

Systematic evaluation of decision-making processes and safety perceptions for donation of electronic health record data in Austria: a mixed-method study

Short title: Health Data Donation Austria

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Kurzfassung (German)

Systematische Untersuchung von Entscheidungsprozessen und Sicherheitsbedürfnissen bei der Spende von Daten der elektronischen Gesundheitsakte in Österreich: Eine mixed-method Studie

Kurztitel: Gesundheitsdatenspende Österreich

1. Rechtfertigung und Relevanz

Die Spende von elektronischen Gesundheitsdaten kann einen wichtigen Beitrag zur Forschung und somit zur Verbesserung der medizinischen Versorgung leisten. In der vorliegenden Studie werden Entscheidungsprozesse und Sicherheitsbedürfnisse bei der Spende von Gesundheitsdaten in Österreich eingehend untersucht. Bisher gibt es nur begrenzte Forschung darüber, wie Bürger:innen/Patient:innen in Österreich zu dieser Thematik stehen. Unzureichend untersucht ist auch welche Erwartungshaltungen Forscher:innen und andere relevante Akteur:innen in Bezug auf die Nutzung von gespendeten Gesundheitsdaten haben. Durch die systematische Erfassung dieser Informationen können wir ein umfassenderes Verständnis für die ethischen Implikationen und die potenziellen Auswirkungen der Nutzung von Gesundheitsdaten gewinnen. Diese Erkenntnisse sind entscheidend für die Gestaltung von Richtlinien und Praktiken im Bereich der Gesundheitsforschung und des Datenschutzes, um sicherzustellen, dass die Interessen der Bürger:innen/Patient:innen angemessen berücksichtigt werden und die Integrität ihrer Daten geschützt wird.

2. Ziele der Studie

Ziel der Studie ist es, verschiedene Aspekte rund um das Thema Datenspende von ELGA-standardisierten Daten aus verschiedenen Perspektiven zu beleuchten. (1) Auf der einen Seite nehmen hierbei die Bedürfnisse, Sicherheitsbedenken, Erwartungshaltungen und Gedanken von Bürger:innen/Patient:innen eine wichtige Rolle ein. (2) Auf der anderen Seite sind auch die Wünsche und Erwartungshaltungen von denjenigen die diese Daten in weiterer Folge nutzen möchten wichtig. In dieser Studie sollen daher die wesentlichen Faktoren für Entscheidungsprozesse und Sicherheitsbedürfnisse rund um die Spende von Daten der elektronischen Gesundheitsakte in Österreich systematisch untersucht werden.

3. Design

In Österreich wird eine mixed-method Studie durchgeführt.

4. Maßnahmen und Vorgehensweise

Durchführung von Interviews

Um unterschiedliche Perspektiven und persönlichen Erfahrungen zum Thema Gesundheitsdatenspende zu erfassen, werden 30 Bürger:innen (15 Personen mit chronischem Krankheitsgeschehen und 15 Personen ohne vorliegende chronische Erkrankungen) rekrutiert. Zusätzlich werden 15 Forscher:innen/Expert:innen eingeschlossen, die mit Sekundärdaten aus dem Gesundheitsbereich arbeiten bzw. über spezifische Fachkenntnisse verfügen.

Die Auswahl der Teilnehmer:innen erfolgt unter Berücksichtigung verschiedener demografischer Merkmale, um ein Sample mit größtmöglicher Varianz zu gewährleisten. Vor der Durchführung von individuellen Interviews erhalten die Teilnehmer:innen einen kurzen, auf die jeweilige Zielgruppe angepassten, Fragebogen. Dieser enthält Fragen, die sich auf die Einstellungen, Meinungen und Bedenken der Teilnehmer:innen in Bezug auf die Spende von Gesundheitsdaten konzentrieren. Zusätzlich werden auch demografische Informationen erfasst, um Unterschiede in den Antworten nach Alter, Geschlecht, Bildungsstand und anderen Variablen analysieren zu können. Die Interviews werden je nach Präferenz der Teilnehmenden online oder vor Ort angeboten und zwischen 45 und 60 Minuten dauern, auf Tonband aufgezeichnet und transkribiert. Die qualitativen Daten werden mittels thematischer Inhaltsanalyse ausgewertet. Für die Analyse quantitativer Daten werden deskriptive Verfahren verwendet.

Durchführung von Fokusgruppen

Um tiefere Einblicke in die Einstellungen, Meinungen und Bedenken der Teilnehmer:innen zu erhalten und Möglichkeit zum Austausch und Diskussion zu geben, werden außerdem auch drei Fokusgruppen durchgeführt. Diese Fokusgruppen werden sowohl unter Bürger:innen/Patient:innen (max. 8 Teilnehmer:innen) als auch unter Forscher:innen/Expert:innen abgehalten (max.16 Personen). Vor der Durchführung der Fokusgruppen erhalten die Teilnehmer:innen einen kurzen, auf die jeweilige Zielgruppe angepassten, Fragebogen, der Fragen zur Gesundheitsdatenspende enthält und demografische Informationen erfasst. Die Diskussionen werden strukturiert sein, um bestimmte, sensible Themen im Zusammenhang mit der Spende von Gesundheitsdaten zu erkunden, einschließlich Datenschutz und -sicherheit, Vertrauen in die Datennutzung und Erwartungen an den Nutzen der Forschung. Ein Treffen wird insgesamt etwa zwei bis maximal drei Stunden in Anspruch nehmen.

Teilnehmer:innen an den Interviews und Fokusgruppen werden über das Schneeballverfahren mit Unterstützung von Patient:innenorganisationen sowie Gesundheits- und Forschungseinrichtungen zur Teilnahme eingeladen und über die Studie informiert.

Durchführung eines Online-Surveys

Zusätzlich zu den Interviews und Fokusgruppen wird mit Hilfe von LimeSurvey ein Online-Survey erstellt, um eine größere Anzahl von Personen zu erreichen und quantitative Daten zu erheben. Das Ziel ist es, mindestens 500 Bürger:innen in ganz Österreich zu erreichen. Der Survey wird Fragen enthalten, die sich auf die Einstellungen, Meinungen und Bedenken der Teilnehmer:innen in Bezug auf die Spende von Gesundheitsdaten konzentrieren. Dabei werden auch demografische Informationen erfasst, um Unterschiede in den Antworten nach Alter, Geschlecht, Bildungsstand und anderen Variablen zu analysieren. Die Beantwortung des Surveys erfolgt anonym, Teilnehmer:innen können daher nicht mehr rückverfolgt bzw. kontaktiert werden.

5. Conclusio

Durch die Auseinandersetzung mit dem komplexen Zusammenspiel von gesellschaftlichen Einstellungen, Stakeholder-Anforderungen und Sicherheitsanforderungen strebt die Studie einen Paradigmenwechsel in der Datenverwaltung in der österreichischen Gesundheitslandschaft an und fördert eine Kultur der Transparenz, des Vertrauens und der verantwortungsvollen Innovation. Die Ergebnisse dieser Studie werden der interessierten Öffentlichkeit in verschiedenen Formaten wie Publikationen und Vorträgen auf Konferenzen zugänglich gemacht.

INTRODUCTION

Subject of research

The donation of electronic health data can make a significant contribution to research and thus to the improvement of medical care. The present study thoroughly examines the decision-making processes, security perceptions and relevance of health data donation in Austria. So far, there is limited research on how citizens/patients in Austria view this issue. Also insufficiently examined is what expectations researchers and other relevant stakeholders have regarding the use of donated health data. By systematically capturing this information, we can gain a more comprehensive understanding of the ethical implications and potential impacts of using health data. These insights are crucial for shaping policies and practices in the field of health research and data protection to ensure that the interests of citizens/patients are adequately considered, and the integrity of their data is protected.

Furthermore, the findings from this study serve as an essential foundation for the Smart FOX project (Smart and Federated Open Data eXchange of Citizen-based Data Donations for Clinical Research) funded by the Austrian research funding agency. The flagship project aims to streamline the process of health data donation by ensuring that it is secure, informed and voluntary, addressing the challenges of privacy and data integration within the Austrian healthcare landscape. Smart FOX aspires not merely to simplify the data donation process for citizens and patients but also to enable their meaningful and secure contribution towards medical progress. Consequently, the knowledge obtained from this study is instrumental in guiding the approaches developed in Smart FOX.

State-of-the-art

The secondary use of health data, in particular, Electronic Health Record (EHR) data, has gained significant attention as a valuable resource for clinical research (Beresniak et al. 2016) including clinical trials (Bruland et al. 2016) clinical registries (Kannan et al. 2017), epidemiological research (Gianfrancesco and Goldstein 2021), pharmacovigilance (Lavertu et al. 2021), and outcomes research (Myers and Stevens 2016). Advanced analytical methods, such as machine learning (ML), natural language processing (NLP) and artificial intelligence (AI) are applied to extract valuable insights from EHR data and improve healthcare outcomes (Kramer et al. 2017). EHR data are increasingly being used to generate real-world evidence (RWE) on the safety, effectiveness, and comparative effectiveness of medical interventions (Manion et al. 2012; Hersh et al. 2013). RWE complements traditional clinical trial data by providing insights into the long-term effects of treatments and the performance of healthcare interventions in real-world settings (e.g., effectiveness vs. efficacy gap) (Hernandez-Boussard et al. 2019; Sherman et al. 2016). However, these benefits can only be realized if researchers can access these data (Strech et al. 2020).

One possible way to gain access to large bodies of HER data is citizen/patient-based data donation. The willingness of patients to donate their personal data for research purposes is documented in various studies, with readiness rates at least 79% (Strech et al. 2020), and often above 80% (Richter et al. 2021; Kalkman et al. 2022).

Standardization and harmonization within Austria's ELGA (Electronic Health Record) system play a crucial role in enhancing efficiency and safety. By establishing uniform standards for storing, transmitting, and utilizing health data, consistent and reliable information exchange is ensured. This promotes interoperability between various healthcare facilities and applications, facilitating seamless communication and coordination. Enhanced access to comprehensive and up-to-date health data allows for informed decision-making and personalized treatment, ultimately improving the quality of care while minimizing the risk of errors. The implementation of ELGA, Austria's opt-out-based EHR, has allowed Austria to establish a strong foundation for collection and exchange of highly standardized health data, governed by a dedicated law. By harnessing existing infrastructures and drawing upon their accumulated expertise, Austria has developed a robust platform for securely storing and sharing health data. This forward-thinking approach not only ensures the seamless continuity of patient records but also facilitates the exchange of information among healthcare providers.

Building on this foundation, the potential donation of these standardized health data emerges as a pivotal opportunity by harnessing the benefits of secondary patient data use, considering scientific recommendations, and maximizing the potential of EHRs and other data sources. The secondary use of these standardized patient data for scientific purposes is considered beneficial, offering advantages like efficient data acquisition, extensive data volume, and electronic data availability (Strech et al. 2020).

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Current obstacles to the donation of health data in Austria

Currently, there are no nationally scaled initiatives to systematically utilize ELGA data for clinical research. This is mainly due to the following obstacles:

- Legal and governance: the ELGA law, currently does not enable the utilization of ELGA information on anything else but healthcare. The Forschungsorganisationsgesetz (FOG) is limiting access to data and involves complex processes for application.
- Infrastructure: currently, there is no national infrastructure for data donation services, including a method for large-scale pseudonymization and privacy-preserving record linkage.
- Capacity building: there is no structured community dedicated to this topic and corresponding capacity building as well promoting the data donation concept to facilitate access to high quality data.
- Data quality: Often the quality of patient generated data is not sufficient to be eligible to be used in clinical research purposes (Abdolkhani et al. 2019). Further assessments need to be conducted, but by using ELGA-standardized datasets high quality and interoperability up to the semantic level can be assumed.

International approaches

Especially in the United States of America (USA), there are several important initiatives to foster the secondary use of data in the context of clinical research, which are most relevant to our study.

The CMS Blue Button 2.0 initiative was developed by the US Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services (CMS). Blue Button 2.0 aims to facilitate the seamless exchange of health information between patients, healthcare providers, and researchers in the USA. CMS allows patients to make informed decisions on donating their health data for research purposes. By leveraging secure and standardized Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), Blue Button 2.0 ensures the privacy and security of sensitive health information. This initiative not only enhances the accessibility and availability of large-scale RWD for research purposes but also empowers individuals to actively participate in advancing medical knowledge and improving patient outcomes (Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services 2023; Singh et al. 2019; Braunstein 2018).

OpenNotes is an initiative that promotes transparency and patient engagement by granting patients access to their clinical notes written by healthcare providers in the USA. It encourages open communication between patients and healthcare professionals and empowers individuals to actively participate in their care by understanding their medical information and making informed decisions (OpenNotes 2023).

The U.S. program “All of Us Research Program”, led by the National Institutes of Health (NIH), aims to gather health data from one million or more participants. The program focuses on diversity and aims to create a source for advancing precision medicine and improving health outcomes. Participants contribute their EHR data, biospecimens, and answer surveys (Denny et al. 2019; Ramirez et al. 2022).

In Germany, the Medical Informatics Initiative is addressing the topic of clinical data donation. Patients can consent to the release of certain health data and biomaterials for research purposes through Broad Consent. This includes data collected during treatments at university hospitals and associated sites, such as information from medical letters, patient history, examination findings, blood pressure measurements, X-ray images, and results of laboratory tests, including genetic analyses.

Additionally, patients can agree to the use of health insurance data from outpatient and inpatient care, requested from health insurance companies, covering medical services, prescribed remedies and aids, medications, and nursing care information (Medizininformatik-Initiative 2020).

Various other countries started noteworthy initiatives to empower patients by giving access to their health data and by improving secondary use of data in clinical research: E.g. My Health Record (Australia) Australian Digital Health Agency 2023, National Electronic Health Record (NEHR) System (Singapore), Connecting for Health (United Kingdom), etc. However, it is important to note that the research facilitated by these programs is not citizen-based, indicating a more traditional approach to data utilization and patient engagement in the research process.

Objectives

Our study aims to shed light on various aspects surrounding the topic of data donation from ELGA-standardized data from different perspectives. (1) On the one hand, the needs, security concerns, expectations, and thoughts of citizens/patients play an important role. (2) On the other hand, the desires and expectations of those who intend to use this data in subsequent applications are important to know. This study aims to systematically investigate the key factors influencing decision-making processes and security perceptions surrounding the donation of data from the electronic health record system in Austria.

Expected impact

The exploration of data donation from ELGA-standardized data represents a pivotal endeavor, with far-reaching implications across various facets of clinical research, healthcare and technology.

The following multifaceted dimensions and potential outcomes are to be expected:

Advancing Understanding of Citizens' and Patients' Perspectives

At the heart of this study lies the endeavor to comprehend citizens' and patients' perspectives, needs, and concerns regarding data donation. By meticulously examining their attitudes, expectations, and apprehensions, the study unveils insights crucial for fostering informed decision-making processes. Through structured investigations and empirical analyses, the study anticipates shedding light on the nuanced intricacies that underpin individuals' willingness to contribute their electronic health records (EHR) data to larger repositories.

The expected impact in this domain transcends mere elucidation of attitudes. By comprehensively understanding the concerns and preferences of citizens and patients, the study seeks to inform policy frameworks, engendering more patient-centric approaches to data governance. This may foster a culture of trust and transparency, essential for sustaining robust data ecosystems within healthcare.

Unraveling Stakeholders' Expectations

In parallel, the study endeavors to probe into the desires and expectations of stakeholders poised to utilize donated EHR data in subsequent applications. This dimension of inquiry represents a novel frontier, offering insights into the needs and requisites of data consumers within the healthcare landscape. By engaging with stakeholders across diverse domains such as research, policymaking, and healthcare provision, the study aims to delineate the contours of their expectations and the requirements of data utilization.

The anticipated impact in this sphere extends beyond theoretical conjecture. By elucidating stakeholder expectations, the study envisages facilitating the development of tailored infrastructures and protocols for data utilization. This may catalyze innovation and collaboration within the healthcare ecosystem, fostering synergies between data donors and data consumers. Moreover, by aligning data utilization practices with stakeholder expectations, the study aspires to fortify the ethical underpinnings of data donation initiatives, mitigating risks and engendering responsible data stewardship.

Informed Decision-Making Processes and Safety Perceptions

Central to the study's objectives is the systematic investigation of key factors influencing decision-making processes and security perceptions surrounding data donation from the EHR in Austria. By employing rigorous methodologies and analytical frameworks, the study endeavors to unearth the determinants shaping individuals' choices and apprehensions regarding data sharing. Furthermore, the study aims to elucidate the intricate interplay between security perceptions and decision-making processes, unraveling the cognitive underpinnings that govern individuals' behaviors in this context.

The study envisages fostering a climate of informed consent and risk awareness among data donors by illuminating the factors that influence decision-making and security perceptions. This may bolster public confidence in data donation initiatives, cultivating a culture of empowerment and agency. Additionally, by delineating strategies to enhance data security and privacy safeguards, the study aims to fortify the resilience of data ecosystems, mitigating vulnerabilities and bolstering societal trust in data-driven healthcare paradigms.

By navigating the intricate interplay between societal attitudes, stakeholder requisites, and security imperatives, the study aspires to engender a paradigm shift in data governance within the Austrian healthcare landscape, fostering a culture of transparency, trust, and responsible innovation.

Knowledge transfer/dissemination

- Presentation of the results at various conferences (e.g., dHealth, Medical Informatics Europe, conference at the end of the project to reach out to relevant other stakeholder groups and inform health policy decision-makers)
- Publication in a scientific journal
- Incorporation of the study results into the ongoing Smart FOX project and future research projects dealing with data donations

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH**Study design and participants**

A mixed-method study will be conducted in Austria. We will offer individual in-depth interviews and focus groups (including short questionnaires), and an online survey to engage the relevant stakeholders actively.

Inclusion criteria: Study participants are citizens over the age of 18 who speak and understand the German language or can take part in German-language interviews/focus groups.

Exclusion criteria: People who are unwilling to give written and oral informed consent, who cannot give consent in person, and people with severe hearing or cognitive impairment who make it impossible to complete (telephone) surveys and participate in interviews/focus groups make.

Qualitative research methods typically use small sample sizes with diverse participants to explore people's personal experiences and views on a specific topic. A maximum variation strategy regarding gender, age, educational level, comorbidity, living situation and other socio-demographic characteristics will be applied (Patton 2015). We anticipate conducting 30 interviews and but will stop sampling once data saturation is achieved (Wengraf 2001; Guetterman 2015; Mosor et al. 2021). Data saturation is defined as no new concepts appearing in at least ten subsequent interviews. First analyses will thus already start when the first transcripts are available and proceed parallel to data collection (Pope et al. 2000). Preliminary results of the interviews will be incorporated in the focus group discussions.

Conducting interviews

In order to capture different perspectives and personal experiences on health data donation, a total of 30 citizens (15 people with chronic diseases and 15 people without chronic diseases) will be recruited. In addition, we will also invite 15 researchers/experts who work with secondary data from the healthcare sector and have specific specialist knowledge for interviews.

The participants are selected, taking various demographic characteristics into account to ensure a sample with the greatest possible variance. Before conducting the individual interviews, participants receive a short questionnaire tailored to the respective target group.

The questions focus on participants' attitudes, opinions and concerns regarding donating health data. Demographic information is also collected to analyze differences in responses based on age, gender, education level and other variables. The interviews will be offered online or on site depending on the participants' preferences, will last between 45 and 60 minutes, and will be audio recorded and transcribed. The qualitative data is evaluated using thematic content analysis. Descriptive methods are used to analyze quantitative data.

Conducting focus groups

To gain deeper insights into the attitudes, opinions and concerns of the participants and to provide an opportunity for exchange and discussion, we will also offer three focus groups. These focus groups will be held with both citizens/patients (max. 8 participants) and researchers/experts (max. 16 people). Before conducting the focus groups, we will ask the participants to fill in demographic data and answer a short questionnaire adapted to the respective target group. Discussions will be structured to explore specific, sensitive topics related to the donation of health data, including privacy and security, trust in data use, and expectations for the usefulness of research. A meeting will take around two to a maximum of three hours.

Participants in the interviews and focus groups will be invited to participate and informed about the study using a snowball process with the support of patient organizations, health- and research institutions.

Conducting an online survey

In addition to the interviews and focus groups, an online survey will be developed by using the tool LimeSurvey and distributed, to reach at least 500 citizens throughout Austria to learn about their opinions and collect more quantitative data on the topic. The survey will contain questions that focus on participants' attitudes, opinions and concerns regarding the donation of health information. Demographic information is also collected to analyze differences in responses based on age, gender, education level and other variables. The survey is answered anonymously. Participants can, therefore, no longer be traced or contacted.

Data collection

Participant characteristic

We will collect a tailored set of characteristics using a case report form (CRF) for each group of participants, recognizing that the specific data needed varies depending on whether the individual is a citizen/patient (data owner) or a researcher/expert (data user). For citizen/patients, information will include their age in years, gender, and education level, alongside information about their place of residence (urban or rural), their self-assessed general health status, any personal affliction with diseases, the specific types of diseases, and the presence of someone with a severe illness in their immediate environment.

For researchers/experts, we will gather data on their age in years, gender, how frequently they use secondary health data, their years of research experience, and their highest attained education level.

Interviews

Researchers and Patient Research Partners have started to co-develop and pilot semi-structured interview guides for the interviews, and the short questionnaires used before the interviews and focus groups (Kvale 1996). The targeted questions will focus on participants' attitudes, opinions and concerns regarding the donation of health data in Austria. The interview guide might be slightly adapted based on additional topics that come up during the interviews and an initial analysis of the interview data.

We will contact patients interested in sharing their views and participating in an interview and/or focus group via the snowball system through patient organizations (e.g., Survivors Austria, Ludwig Boltzmann Institute for Digital Health and Patient Safety, Österreichische Morbus Crohn/Colitis ulcerosa Vereinigung, Österreichische Rheumaliga) and the Medical University of Vienna.

As a first step, patient and health organizations will be contacted by a study team member at the Medical University of Vienna by telephone or email. Suppose they are interested in the study and are willing to recruit participants in principle. In that case, they will receive the informed consent and study flyer (for information), and the telephone number and email address of Erika Mosor (senior researcher at the Institute for Outcomes Research) by email. The patient organizations and outpatient clinics will then contact possible participants, who will be asked to contact Erika Mosor themselves if interested in the study participation.

Interested citizens, researchers and experts in the field will be contacted by members of the project team and different social media channels of the Smart FOX project.

During the first contact, experienced researchers in the field of qualitative research from the study team will inform the individuals about the study. In the event of oral consent, an interview appointment will be made. The interview will take place at the Medical University of Vienna, the Austrian Institute of Technology in Vienna or virtually, depending on the interviewees' preferences.

The participant will give written consent before starting the interview and will fill in the CRF and the questionnaire. If the interview is done remotely (by phone or MS Teams), the informed consent form, the CRF and the questionnaire will be sent to the participant either per email or by post along with a stamped return envelope. Once all questions have been answered, we ask the participants to return the signed consent forms and the other documents in the return envelope to the MUW or email them to studie@smart-fox.at, if desired.

The interviews will last between 45 and 60 minutes. All interviews will be audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim.

Focus groups

Subsequently, we will organise the three focus groups. The focus groups will take place at the Medical University of Vienna or at the Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT). Around eight participants will be invited to join one focus group. (Akoglu & Dankl, 2021) We plan to conduct one focus group with citizens/patients, and two with researchers and experts in the field (also including patient advocates). The participants will give written consent before starting the focus group and will fill in the CRF and the questionnaire. Discussions will be structured to explore specific topics related to health data donation, including perceptions of privacy and security, trust in data use, and expectations of research usefulness. Each meeting will last 120-180 minutes. The process of each focus group will be accompanied and documented by two moderators experienced in qualitative research following non-hierarchical forms of moderation in which the joint- and mutual learning processes will be fully respected (Akoglu and Dankl 2021).

Online Survey

The online survey will contain questions that focus on participants' attitudes, opinions and concerns regarding donation of health information. Demographic information is also collected to analyze differences in responses based on age, gender, education level and other variables (see participant characteristic).

Participants for the online survey will be informed about the study and invited to participate with the support of patient organizations, display of flyers at various health facilities, social media postings, newsletters and a patient recruitment service (Probando GmbH).

The data will be collected with a LimeSurvey (Englert et al. 2023; LimeSurvey GmbH n.d.) instance ensuring anonymity of the participants.

Data analysis

Descriptive statistics will be applied to summarize the characteristics of participants. We will use R-Statistics (The R Foundation 2024; Field et al. 2012) for all calculations.

Thematic analysis of qualitative data will follow a modified form of 'meaning condensation' (Kvale 1996), facilitated by MAXQDA software (Rädiker and Kuckartz 2019) to manage and organize the data. Thematic analysis will comprise the following steps:

All transcripts will be screened and read by researchers of the study team. Data will then be divided into meaning units (defined as specific text parts, either a few words or sentences with a common meaning). All types of information that might allow re-identification of participants will be deleted from the meaning units. E.g., if a name, location, position, a healthcare provider, or a specific clinic will be mentioned by the interviewee, this information will be replaced with "xxx". Transcripts will not be shared with other study participants. The researchers will then group associated meaning units into lower-level themes and summarise them into higher-level themes.

The online survey will be analysed with the LimeSurvey built in analytics tools. Further analyses (including the data from the questionnaires provided by the interviewees and focus group participants) will be performed with exports of the data set in R-statistics.

Based on the findings from the interviews, questionnaires, focus groups and the online survey the study team will develop recommendations for the governance of data donations. These recommendations including a lay version will be finalised with the input of representatives of all stakeholder groups. Both versions will be disseminated afterwards.

Rigor and accuracy of the study

We will record reflective memos and debriefing notes after each interview and focus group. Accuracy of the analysis will be ensured by having at least 10% of the data analyzed by another investigator. The consolidated criteria for reporting qualitative research (COREQ) Checklist (Tong et al. 2007) will be used to ensure the high quality of reporting of the qualitative study results.

Ethical considerations

The study will be approved by the ethics committees of the Medical University of Vienna. After being informed about the study's purpose and procedures, the participants will give their oral and written informed consent following the Declaration of Helsinki (World Medical Association, 2013) and all applicable local regulations. According to the participant's will, data previously recorded could be kept in the database for analysis or deleted. Participants have access to their data on request and the right to correct them if incorrect data was recorded.

Patient Research Partners

Patient Research Partners are part of the Smart FOX project team and included in all stages of the study. They ensure that participants are not overburdened, the documents are easy to understand and will support disseminating the study results in lay language.

Data security

Data that we collect from this study will be kept confidential. Collected information about the participating person during the research study will be secured against unauthorized access and stored safely at the Medical University of Vienna. Professional confidentiality rules bind all study personnel. Only pseudonymized data will be shared with project partners. For other researchers and research institutions, data will be completely anonymized. Likewise, publications of this mixed-method study will not include any personal information which might lead to the identification of participants. Participants have the right to submit a complaint to the national data protection agency about handling their data at any time.

Benefit/risk evaluation

No risks are to be expected from participating in the study. Interviews and focus groups will be offered face-to-face or virtually, depending on the participants' preferences. Patient involvement will be restricted to a maximum of one in-depth interview and one focus group to minimize the burden.

Suppose people feel bad about the interview or the focus group and are looking for psychosocial support to help deal with their situation. In that case, we will advise them to consult appropriate services, such as telephone counselling (Sorgetelefon) for people in crisis and difficult life situations, which is offered free of charge, confidentially and professionally around the clock under the nationwide emergency number 142.

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